

Comparative Study of Soft and Hard Boundary Constraints in Physics-Informed Neural Networks for Quantum Mechanical Eigenvalue Problems

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Abstract

Developing methods to accurately and efficiently solve the Schrödinger equation is important for advancing computational studies in quantum physics and chemistry. In this work, we embed physical and mathematical constraints into unsupervised neural network training to solve the Schrödinger equation for different potentials and focus on comparing the performance of models trained with soft and hard boundary constraints. We benchmark the solutions against analytical results when available, or numerical solvers otherwise, to assess accuracy. For the harmonic oscillator, the soft-constrained model accurately predicts multiple excited states but requires more training epochs and fails for the Coulomb and the screened Coulomb potentials when the angular momentum is not zero. Hard-constrained models can converge more efficiently, though their success depends strongly on the chosen formulation. In particular, ansätze that reflect the asymptotic behavior of solutions and include a learnable parameter achieve accurate results with fewer epochs. Additional gains in both accuracy and efficiency are obtained by employing adaptive learning rate scheduling based on the differential equation residual.

Keywords: Physics-informed neural networks, Boundary constraints, Schrödinger equation, Eigenvalue problems, Machine learning, Computational physics

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1. Introduction

Machine learning methods have grown in popularity with applications in fields such as computer vision, natural language processing, and scientific modeling by finding patterns in data to make predictions. In a supervised setting, given input and output pairs, neural networks can be tuned to learn the underlying target function. These techniques have been used to solve various physics problems in astrophysics, particle physics, materials science, biophysics and quantum mechanics [1, 2, 3, 4, 5].

Traditional machine learning methods rely heavily on large amounts of data to train the models and do not actually learn the dynamics of the physical system they are modeling. In order to address these issues, recently a class of neural networks called physics-informed neural networks (PINNs) have been developed [6]. PINNs incorporate the governing partial differential equation (PDE) as a loss function during training to approximate the solutions. Unlike traditional numerical solvers that approximate solutions in a discretized domain, solutions from PINNs are in analytical form and easily differentiable [7]. By embedding system physics during training, PINNs perform well even with scarce or noisy data [8]. Consequently, PINNs find their applications in physics, solving both forward problems and inverse problems such as finding solutions to Navier-Stokes equations, heat transfer problems, characterization of defects in materials and recovering parameters from MRI scans [9, 10, 11, 12].

PINNs can also be employed to solve the quantum mechanical eigenvalue problems. By formulating the Schrödinger equation as a loss function to minimize with respect to network parameters, ground state energies and wave functions can be found [13]. Including normalization conditions, boundary conditions and orthonormality conditions as losses along with the differential equation, a neural network can be trained to learn multiple solutions to the Schrödinger equation [14]. Another class of neural network solver of ordinary differential equations called Deep Ritz method minimizes a variational functional, specifically the Rayleigh quotient, which is analogous to using a neural network as the variational ansatz in the variational method in quantum mechanics [15]. This method has been used to solve the eigenvalue problems for infinite well and harmonic oscillator [16]. Equipped with efficient sampling strategies, PINNs can also provide a viable approach for solving two-dimensional quantum problems, such as decoupled and coupled harmonic oscillators [17]. Optimizing PINNs using analytically derived gra-

dients of the loss function, rather than numerical approximations, has been shown to improve convergence [18].

In order to enforce boundary conditions, models can be trained with soft or hard constraints. Effects of using PINNs with soft and hard boundary constraints are studied for solving Navier-Stokes equation, wave equation, and Poisson equation [19, 20, 21]. Although studies using both soft and hard constraints are prevalent in the literature for quantum systems, we do not find investigations specifically comparing the influence of these techniques. Hence, in this study, we focus on comparing the accuracy and efficiency of PINNs with different formulations of boundary constraints in solving the Schrödinger equation.

2. Formulations and Methods

2.1. Schrödinger Equation

In non-relativistic quantum mechanics, the time-dependent Schrödinger equation:

$$i\hbar \frac{d|\Psi(t)\rangle}{dt} = \hat{H}|\Psi(t)\rangle \quad (1)$$

governs the time evolution of the state vector $|\Psi(t)\rangle$, which belongs to \mathcal{H} , a separable complex Hilbert space, and is postulated to contain all the information about the physical state at time t [22, 23, 24]. Restricting ourselves to time-independent Hamiltonian operators \hat{H} and choosing the position representation, \hat{H} assumes the form $-\frac{\hbar^2}{2m} \frac{d^2}{dx^2} + V(x)$ for a particle of mass m bound in a real one-dimensional potential $V(x) : \mathbb{R} \rightarrow \mathbb{R}$. Under these conditions, and assuming that Eq. (1) has solutions $\Psi(x, t) = \langle x|\Psi(t)\rangle$ that can be written as a product of a time-dependent function $\phi(t)$ and a space-dependent function $\psi(x)$, we obtain two separate differential equations, one for each function. Solving for $\phi(t)$ yields merely a phase factor $e^{\frac{-iEt}{\hbar}}$. With this in mind, we can focus only on solving the time-independent Schrödinger equation:

$$-\frac{\hbar^2}{2m} \frac{d^2\psi(x)}{dx^2} + V(x)\psi(x) = E\psi(x), \quad (2)$$

which is an eigenvalue problem. In this study, we seek a set of non-trivial energy eigenvalues $E \in \mathbb{R}$ and the corresponding eigenfunctions (called the wave

functions) $\psi(x) \in L^2(\mathbb{R})$, the Hilbert space of square-integrable complex-valued functions on \mathbb{R} , i.e.

$$\langle \Psi(t) | \Psi(t) \rangle = \int_{\mathbb{R}} \Psi(x, t) \Psi^*(x, t) dx = \int_{\mathbb{R}} |\psi(x)|^2 dx < \infty, \quad (3)$$

that satisfy Eq. (2). Although the Hermiticity of \hat{H} guarantees real eigenvalues, the eigenfunctions need not be real in general. For bound states in one-dimensional systems with real time-independent potentials, however, the eigenfunctions may always be taken to be real. This is why our model is designed to produce only real $\psi(x)$. Accordingly, in the treatment that follows, we restrict ourselves to real-valued $\psi(x)$.

The square integrability of the wave functions is a direct consequence of considering bound states. This condition leads to normalizable wave functions, thereby allowing the physical interpretation of $|\psi(x)|^2$ as a probability density of finding the particle at position x in accordance with the Born's rule. The boundedness of the particle and the normalizability of the wave function necessitate the following asymptotic behavior:

$$\psi(x) \rightarrow 0 \quad \text{as} \quad |x| \rightarrow \infty. \quad (4)$$

A one-dimensional bound system has a discrete and non-degenerate energy spectrum. Two non-degenerate eigenfunctions ψ_1 and ψ_2 are orthogonal to one-another, i.e.

$$\langle \Psi_1(t) | \Psi_2(t) \rangle = \int_{\mathbb{R}} \psi_1(x) \psi_2(x) dx = 0, \quad (5)$$

due to the hermiticity of \hat{H} . This property proves useful when seeking wave functions orthogonal to those already obtained by our model.

We also attempt at solving the Schrödinger equation for two particles of mass m_1 and m_2 interacting via spherically symmetric potentials, also known as central potentials, $V(r)$ defined on $(0, \infty)$ or $[0, \infty)$. If we fix the origin of r on one of the particles, this two body problem can effectively be transformed into a single body problem by considering the motion of the reduced mass $\mu = \frac{m_1 m_2}{m_1 + m_2}$, relative to the origin, confined in $V(r)$. It should be noted that the motion of the center of mass $m_1 + m_2$ must also be accounted for. However, since this motion reduces to that of a free particle, it does not warrant further attention. The three-dimensional form of Eq. (2) for μ in

spherical coordinates can be separated into angular parts and a radial part. We examine only the radial part in this study. If $R(r)$ is the radial solution, the radial part of the equation can be written as:

$$-\frac{\hbar^2}{2\mu} \frac{d^2\zeta(r)}{dr^2} + \left[V(r) + \frac{l(l+1)\hbar^2}{2\mu r^2} \right] \zeta(r) = E\zeta(r), \quad (6)$$

where $\zeta(r) = rR(r)$ (sometimes called the reduced radial wave function), and l is the orbital angular momentum quantum number. For bound states, $\zeta(r)$ must satisfy the following boundary conditions:

$$\zeta(r) \rightarrow 0 \quad \text{as } r \rightarrow 0, \infty. \quad (7)$$

Notice that $R(r)$ diverges at origin if $\zeta(0) \neq 0$. Since we are working in spherical coordinates in this case, the orthonormality condition takes the form:

$$\int_0^\infty R_n(r)R_{n'}(r)r^2dr = \delta_{nn'}. \quad (8)$$

The above formulation assumes the spinless approximation.

2.2. Physics Informed Neural Network

Consider a differential equation of the form $D_x u(x) = 0$, where D_x is some differential operator acting upon $u(x)$ w.r.t. x , defined on a domain $\{x : x \in \Omega \subseteq \mathbb{R}\}$ subject to certain boundary (or initial) conditions on the boundary $\partial\Omega$. Let $\Xi_c = \{x_j\}_{j=1}^{N_c} \subset \Omega$ be a finite set of collocation points in the domain. Let $u_\Theta : \Omega \rightarrow \mathbb{R}$ represent a neural network intended to approximate the unknown solution $u(x)$ ($\psi(x)$ in our case). We can then define the following differential equation residual:

$$\mathcal{L}_D(\Theta) = \frac{1}{N_c} \sum_{j=1}^{N_c} (D_x u_\Theta(x_j))^2; \quad x_j \in \Xi_c \quad (9)$$

With this, the differential equation is transformed into an optimization problem where the goal is to find an appropriate set of parameters Θ (set of weights and biases discussed in Section 2.3) such that the residual \mathcal{L}_D is minimized.

Parameters are initialized according to an appropriate initialization scheme [25, 26] and then iteratively updated at each training epoch using optimization algorithms [27, 28, 29, 30, 31, 32, 33]. The majority of modern neural

networks are trained using gradient-based optimization methods. The gradient of the loss function with respect to parameters, $\nabla_{\Theta} \mathcal{L}_D$, required by such algorithms are efficiently computed using backpropagation [34, 35]. Backpropagation applies the chain rule of differentiation to propagate gradients backwards through the network layers, from the output loss to each parameter. This process relies on automatic differentiation (autodiff) [36] to construct the computational graph and evaluate derivatives automatically. The same autodiff framework computes derivatives involved in D_x (see Eq. (2) and (6)).

Beyond embedding the differential equation directly in the network’s loss function, incorporating additional known constraints helps narrow the space of admissible solutions and guides the network toward physically and mathematically consistent solutions. For bound states in our study, the wave functions must vanish at infinity. These constraints can be enforced using two major approaches:

- **Soft Boundary Constraints:** If we wish to impose Dirichlet boundary conditions, such as $\zeta(0) = 0$, we select a collocation boundary set $\Xi_b = \{x_i\}_{i=1}^{N_b} \subseteq \partial\Omega$ and penalize deviations from the prescribed boundary values by introducing the boundary loss:

$$\mathcal{L}_B(\Theta) = \frac{1}{N_b} \sum_{j=1}^{N_b} (u_{\Theta}(x_j) - u(x_j))^2; \quad x_j \in \Xi_b. \quad (10)$$

In problems with unbounded domains, such as ours, the absence of a physical boundary precludes direct imposition of Dirichlet boundary conditions. We instead enforce the correct asymptotic behavior by introducing truncation points (artificial boundary) beyond which the solution satisfies the desired conditions approximately. In this work, $\Xi_b \subset \Xi_c$, $\Xi_b =$ artificial boundary $\partial\Omega$, and $N_b = 2$.

- **Hard Boundary Constraints:** Rather than adding a separate boundary loss term, the neural output $u_{\Theta}(x)$ can be reparameterized in the form of the following ansatz:

$$u_{\Theta}(x)f(x) + g(x), \quad (11)$$

where $f(x)$ and $g(x)$ are chosen such that the resulting expression satisfies the prescribed boundary conditions by construction. This approach

ensures that the solution fulfills the Dirichlet boundary conditions exactly, independent of Θ , while also providing a natural way to impose desired asymptotic behavior. We can choose different functional forms of $f(x)$ for the same boundary conditions or asymptotic behavior. Soft boundary constraints directly affect boundary values but rely on \mathcal{L}_D to indirectly influence the interior points of the solution. In contrast, hard boundary constraints directly shape the solution throughout the entire domain.

To prevent convergence to the trivial solution and enforce normalization, we introduce a norm loss defined as:

$$\mathcal{L}_N(\Theta) = \left[\sum_{j=1}^{N_c-1} u_{\Theta}^2(x_j) \delta x_j - 1 \right]^2 ; x_j \in \Xi_c, \quad (12)$$

where $\delta x_j = x_{j+1} - x_j$ assuming Ξ_c is ordered. The sum term in \mathcal{L}_N is simply an approximation of the integral in condition (3).

When the model has found a set of N_o non-degenerate wave functions¹ $\{u_{\Theta_k}^k\}_{k=1}^{N_o}$, we construct the following loss function based on the orthogonality condition (5) or (8) to allow the network to discover a new wave function $v_{\Theta'}$ orthogonal to all the previously found eigenfunctions:

$$\mathcal{L}_O(\Theta) = \sum_{k=1}^{N_o} \left[\sum_{j=1}^{N_c-1} u_{\Theta_k}^k(x_j) v_{\Theta'}(x_j) \delta x_j \right]^2 ; x_j \in \Xi_c. \quad (13)$$

This orthogonality loss is omitted when only the ground state solution is sought.

The Rayleigh quotient (Rayleigh-Ritz ratio) for an operator \hat{H} and a state vector $|\Psi(t)\rangle$ is defined as:

$$\langle \hat{H} \rangle = \frac{\langle \Psi(t) | \hat{H} | \Psi(t) \rangle}{\langle \Psi(t) | \Psi(t) \rangle}, \quad (14)$$

which is the expectation value of \hat{H} for the state $|\Psi(t)\rangle$. During each epoch, once the network has produced an eigenfunction approximation u_{Θ} , we eval-

¹In Def. (13), the superscript k identifies unique wave functions (not a power, as in (12)), whereas the subscript denotes distinct parameter sets.

uate $\langle \hat{H} \rangle$ using the following expression:

$$E_{\Theta} = \frac{\sum_{j=1}^{N_c-1} u_{\Theta}(x_j) \hat{H} u_{\Theta}(x_j) \delta x_j}{\sum_{j=1}^{N_c-1} u_{\Theta}^2(x_j) \delta x_j}; \quad x_j \in \Xi_c, \quad (15)$$

to approximate the energy eigenvalue. The derivatives involved in the numerator are again computed using autodiff.

We guide the model toward learning eigenfunctions in ascending energy order, starting from the ground state, by including the approximated energy E_{Θ} into the total loss function. For certain potentials, where it is conventional to distinguish bound and scattering states by the sign of energy, we discourage the model to predict positive energies by penalizing the sign loss:

$$\mathcal{L}_S(\Theta) = \max\{0, E_{\Theta}\}. \quad (16)$$

\mathcal{L}_S outputs the larger of 0 and E_{Θ} , so it contributes nothing to the total loss if the predicted energy is negative.

For potentials with negative bound-state energies under soft boundary constraints, we express the total loss function by assembling all the loss components discussed above as follows:

$$\mathcal{L}(\Theta) = \lambda_D \mathcal{L}_D + \lambda_B \mathcal{L}_B + \lambda_N \mathcal{L}_N + \lambda_O \mathcal{L}_O + \lambda_E E_{\Theta} + \lambda_S \mathcal{L}_S. \quad (17)$$

Here, λ coefficients are scalar weights that control the relative importance of each component in the total loss. Formally, our problem of solving a differential equation is now finding

$$\Theta^* = \arg \min_{\Theta} \mathcal{L}(\Theta), \quad (18)$$

the optimal set of parameters that minimizes the total loss function $\mathcal{L}(\Theta)$.

2.3. Network Architecture

We use a fully connected neural network (see Fig. 1) consisting of a single hidden layer with N_h neurons implemented using PyTorch [37], whose automatic differentiation efficiently computes the derivatives required for evaluating the differential equation residual and performing backpropagation during training.

We represent the input to the neural network by a PyTorch tensor $\mathbf{x} \in \mathbb{R}^{N \times 1}$. This is referred to as having a shape of $[N, 1]$ with N indicating the

Figure 1: Neural network with single-featured input, a N_h -sized hidden layer, and single-featured output. The symbol \odot denotes the Hadamard product (or the Schur product), i.e. element-wise product of the tensors \mathbf{u}_Θ and $f(\mathbf{x})$ in the hard-constraint formulation. All the results presented in Section 3 are based on tanh activation with $N_h = 20$, unless stated otherwise.

number of single-featured samples from Ξ_c being fed to the adjacent layer each epoch of the training session. In this work, we choose $N = N_c$. When the input is passed forward from the input layer to the hidden layer, we apply a linear transformation:

$$\mathbf{y} = \mathbf{x}({}^1\mathbf{W})^T + {}^1\mathbf{b}, \quad (19)$$

where the weight tensor ${}^1\mathbf{W} \in \mathbb{R}^{N_h \times 1}$, bias tensor ${}^1\mathbf{b} \in \mathbb{R}^{N_h}$, and $\mathbf{y} \in \mathbb{R}^{N \times N_h}$. PyTorch automatically broadcasts the bias tensor to match the shape of the matrix product $\mathbf{x}({}^1\mathbf{W})^T$ for the element-wise addition to each row of the matrix product. This linear transformation is followed by the application of a non-linear activation function such as \sin [38] or \tanh . For obtaining \mathbf{u}_Θ we apply a linear map to the activation of \mathbf{y} :

$$\begin{aligned} \mathbf{u}_\Theta &= \tanh(\mathbf{y})({}^2\mathbf{W})^T + {}^2\mathbf{b} \\ &= \tanh(\mathbf{x}({}^1\mathbf{W})^T + {}^1\mathbf{b})({}^2\mathbf{W})^T + {}^2\mathbf{b}, \end{aligned} \quad (20)$$

where ${}^2\mathbf{W} \in \mathbb{R}^{1 \times N_h}$, ${}^2\mathbf{b} \in \mathbb{R}$, and $\mathbf{u}_\Theta \in \mathbb{R}^{N \times 1}$.

When making use of hard boundary constraints involving an unknown parameter $\alpha \in \mathbb{R}_{>0}$, we treat it as a learnable parameter of the network. We apply the softplus activation function:

$$\text{softplus}(\alpha) = \log(1 + e^\alpha) \quad (21)$$

to restrict α to positive values.

For our network, the set of trainable parameters is

$$\Theta = \{^1\mathbf{W}, ^1\mathbf{b}, ^2\mathbf{W}, ^2\mathbf{b}, \alpha\}. \quad (22)$$

We employ PyTorch’s default parameter initialization and train the network by iteratively updating these parameters with the Adam optimizer [39].

2.4. Learning Rate

The learning rate η is a positive scalar that controls the step size in the parameter update during optimization. It requires careful selection since overly large values may lead to divergence, whereas overly small values produce slow convergence. We set $\eta = 1 \times 10^{-3}$ for comparison experiments and explore adaptive scheduling for potential improvements.

Although Adam adapts per-parameter learning rates, we additionally modulate the global learning rate based on \mathcal{L}_D evaluated on the current set of parameters Θ_k , clamped within predefined bounds L_{\min} and L_{\max} :

$$L = \max\{\min\{\mathcal{L}_D(\Theta_k), L_{\max}\}, L_{\min}\}, \quad (23)$$

by linearly interpolating η between η_{\min} and η_{initial} :

$$\eta = \eta_{\min} + \kappa(\eta_{\text{initial}} - \eta_{\min}), \quad (24)$$

where $\kappa = \frac{L - L_{\min}}{L_{\max} - L_{\min}}$; $0 \leq \kappa \leq 1$.

This scheduling allows the optimizer to take large steps when the solution is still far from convergence, and progressively smaller steps as it nears the optimal solution. We apply this only after the norm and orthogonality losses fall below a certain threshold.

2.5. Convergence Criteria

We monitor the model’s energy history and declare convergence when the energy begins to saturate. More specifically, we define a fixed window size and compute the average of the most recent energy values within that

window whenever the current epoch is divisible by the window size. We also introduce a patience parameter. When the difference between successive window averages remains below a given threshold for a number of times equal to the patience value, we stop the training. It is important to note that the solutions at convergence are not necessarily used as the final predicted solutions. Instead, we select the solutions corresponding to the lowest differential equation residual encountered during the course of training. We use this criteria only for comparison experiments.

2.6. Experiments and Metrics

The harmonic oscillator problem:

$$V(x) = \frac{1}{2}m\omega^2x^2; \quad x \in \mathbb{R} \quad (25)$$

makes for a good starting point, as the potential is smooth, free of singularities, and has analytical solutions available. We choose a collocation set Ξ_c consisting of 2×10^3 uniformly spaced points in the interval $[-8, 8]$. With this choice, δx_j in Def. (12), (13), (15), and (33) becomes constant, equal to the spacing between consecutive points in Ξ_c .

We set an artificial boundary $\Xi_b = \{-8, 8\}$, where the wave functions have decayed sufficiently to satisfy the asymptotic behavior. For the hard boundary constraints implementation, we consider three different choices for the function f :

$$\text{HBC}_1 : f(x) = (1 - e^{-(x-x_1)})(1 - e^{(x-x_2)}), \quad (26)$$

$$\text{HBC}_2 : f(x) = e^{-\alpha x^2}, \quad (27)$$

$$\text{HBC}_3 : f(x) = e^{-\frac{1}{2}x^2}, \quad (28)$$

with $g(x) = 0$, $x \in \Xi_c$, $x_1, x_2 \in \Xi_b$, and $\alpha \in \mathbb{R}_{>0}$ treated as a learnable parameter. HBC_1 guarantees that the wave functions vanish at x_1 and x_2 , while HBC_2 and HBC_3 mimic the asymptotic behavior of the true wave functions.

In a single training run, we obtain ten solutions. Once the model converges to a solution, we save the network parameter for the best solution and then proceed to the next state without reinitializing the network. For the convergence criteria, we choose a window size of 100 and a patience parameter of 3 with a suitable difference threshold (10^{-12} to 10^{-8}). To assess

the robustness of the method against random parameters initialization, we repeat the training process $N_r = 10$ times and analyze the consistency of the results.

For the n^{th} eigenstate (ψ_n) energy predicted by the model, we define the root mean square relative error (RMSRE) over the N_r independent runs as:

$$\text{RMSRE}_n = \sqrt{\frac{1}{N_r} \sum_{j=1}^{N_r} \left[\frac{E_n - E_{n,\Theta_j}}{E_n} \right]^2}, \quad (29)$$

where

$$E_n = \left(n + \frac{1}{2} \right) \hbar\omega; \quad n \in \mathbb{Z}_{\geq 0}, \quad (30)$$

provides the true energy eigenvalues. Similarly, the predicted wave functions are compared against the analytical solutions:

$$\psi_n = \sqrt{\frac{\sqrt{\gamma}}{\sqrt{\pi}2^n n!}} e^{-\frac{\gamma x^2}{2}} H_n(\sqrt{\gamma}x); \quad n \in \mathbb{Z}_{\geq 0}, \quad (31)$$

where $\gamma = \frac{m\omega}{\hbar}$ and

$$H_n(x) = (-1)^n e^{x^2} \frac{d^n}{dx^n} e^{-x^2}; \quad n \in \mathbb{Z}_{\geq 0} \quad (32)$$

is the n^{th} degree Hermite polynomial. To quantify the faithfulness of these predicted wave functions ψ_{n,Θ_k} to their analytical counterparts ψ_n , we compute the fidelity, also known as overlap:

$$F_n = \sum_{j=1}^{N_c-1} \psi_n(x_j) \psi_{n,\Theta_k}(x_j) \delta x_j; \quad x_j \in \Xi_c. \quad (33)$$

This quantity is computed for each run and averaged over the N_r trials. For a pair of perfectly normalized wave functions, $-1 \leq F \leq 1$ with 1 indicating perfect overlap. We also record the training epochs required by the model to meet the convergence criteria.

Next, we use our model to solve the hydrogen problem:

$$V(r) = \frac{-e}{4\pi\epsilon_0 r}; \quad r \in \mathbb{R}^+. \quad (34)$$

The Coulomb potential has a singularity at $r = 0$. To circumvent this issue, we sample 2×10^3 evenly spaced points from the interval $[0.01, 60]$ for Ξ_c . For hard-constraining the model, we employ HBC₁ and HBC₄:

$$\text{HBC}_4 : f(x) = e^{-\alpha x} x^{l+1}; \quad g(x) = 0; \quad \alpha \in \mathbb{R}_{\geq 0}. \quad (35)$$

We compare the predicted energy eigenvalues to the exact energies given by

$$E_n = -\frac{\mu e^4}{32\pi^2 \epsilon_0^2 \hbar^2 n^2}; \quad n \in \mathbb{Z}^+, \quad (36)$$

and compute the fidelity against the closed-form solutions for a given $n \in \mathbb{Z}^+$ and $l \in \{0, 1, 2, \dots, n-1\}$:

$$R_{nl} = \sqrt{\left(\frac{2}{na_0}\right)^3 \frac{(n-l-1)!}{2n(n+l)!} e^{-\frac{r}{na_0}} \left(\frac{2r}{na_0}\right)^l L_{n-l-1}^{2l+1}\left(\frac{2r}{na_0}\right)}, \quad (37)$$

where $a_0 = \frac{4\pi\epsilon_0\hbar^2}{\mu e^2}$ is the Bohr's radius and

$$L_q^p(x) = \frac{x^{-p} e^x}{q!} \frac{d^q}{dx^q} e^{-x} x^{p+q}; \quad p, q \in \mathbb{Z}_{\geq 0} \quad (38)$$

is the associated (or generalized) Laguerre polynomial [40].

Finally, we attempt to solve the Schrödinger equation for the Yukawa potential. The Yukawa potential defined as:

$$V(r) = -V_0 \frac{e^{-\beta r}}{r}; \quad r \in \mathbb{R}^+, \quad (39)$$

where β is the screening parameter and V_0 controls the strength of the potential, was used by Yukawa to explain strong interaction of proton and neutron in the nucleus of an atom [41]. It is a screened Coulomb potential which reduces to coulomb potential when $\beta = 0$.

We define a constant $g = \frac{\beta}{V_0}$, and in our experiments we set $g = 0.025$ with $V_0 = \sqrt{2}$. We choose 2×10^3 evenly distributed points in $[0.01, 50]$ for Ξ_c . Motivated by the asymptotic analysis of Eq. (6), we choose HBC₄ as the hard boundary constraint on this problem.

Since there is no closed form solution to the Yukawa potential, in order to make a comparison, we use numerical solutions from a finite difference scheme described in [Appendix A](#).

In our testing, λ parameters set to 100 for all the loss components (1 or 10 for E) worked well for Yukawa and Coulomb potential. Different combination of values can be tested for good results.

2.7. Units

We adopt atomic units (a.u.) in this study for numerical stability. In this system of units, e , \hbar , m_e , and $4\pi\epsilon_0$ all equate to 1. Energy is measured in hartree (E_h). For further simplicity, we set $\omega = 1 E_h\hbar^{-1}$ and $m = \mu = m_e$. This choice also makes $\gamma = a_0 = 1$.

3. Results and Discussion

3.1. One-Dimensional Harmonic Oscillator

Figure 2: Wave functions of a quantum harmonic oscillator predicted by the model, from the ground state ($n = 0$) to the ninth excited state ($n = 9$). Not all boundary constraint enforcement variations are shown, as they exhibit nearly perfect overlap.

We present the resulting wave functions in Fig. 2. The model converges to wave functions sequentially, in order of increasing energy. The predicted wave functions demonstrate a high degree of overlap with the corresponding analytical solutions given by Eq. (31). As shown in the third major column of Table 1, SBC and HBC₁ achieve near-perfect average fidelity across all states. HBC₂ achieves accurate results up to the seventh excited state, but shows a drop in fidelity thereafter. HBC₃, however, results in a slight drop in fidelity for the fourth excited state and fails to converge to higher states within the allotted training epochs.

The energy convergence behavior is presented in Fig. 3 (left). Under SBC and HBC₁, the model transitions more smoothly between successive energy

n	$\bar{E}(E_h)$				RMSRE				\bar{F}			
	SBC	HBC ₁	HBC ₂	HBC ₃	SBC	HBC ₁	HBC ₂	HBC ₃	SBC	HBC ₁	HBC ₂	HBC ₃
0	0.5000	0.5000	0.5000	0.5000	6.6×10^{-6}	5.5×10^{-6}	2.1×10^{-6}	2.1×10^{-6}	1.0000	1.0000	1.0005	1.0000
1	1.5000	1.5000	1.5000	1.5000	4.6×10^{-6}	1.4×10^{-5}	5.7×10^{-7}	2.8×10^{-6}	1.0000	1.0000	1.0000	1.0000
2	2.5000	2.5000	2.5000	2.5001	4.1×10^{-6}	6.4×10^{-6}	1.2×10^{-5}	5.0×10^{-5}	1.0000	1.0000	0.9999	0.9996
3	3.5000	3.5000	3.5001	3.5004	1.0×10^{-5}	1.2×10^{-5}	2.8×10^{-5}	1.2×10^{-4}	0.9998	0.9999	0.9997	0.9989
4	4.5001	4.5000	4.5002	4.5153	1.6×10^{-5}	1.2×10^{-5}	6.3×10^{-5}	3.5×10^{-3}	0.9996	0.9998	0.9993	0.9823
5	5.5001	5.5001	5.5003		1.7×10^{-5}	1.2×10^{-5}	8.1×10^{-5}		0.9994	0.9997	0.9992	
6	6.5002	6.5001	6.5001		2.6×10^{-5}	2.1×10^{-5}	4.1×10^{-5}		0.9996	0.9993	0.9996	
7	7.5002	7.5001	7.5004		2.4×10^{-5}	2.0×10^{-5}	1.6×10^{-5}		0.9993	0.9992	0.9987	
8	8.5002	8.5002	8.4003		2.3×10^{-5}	3.6×10^{-5}	3.7×10^{-2}		0.9993	0.9991	0.8991	
9	9.5003	9.5003	9.0021		3.9×10^{-5}	2.9×10^{-5}	1.3×10^{-1}		0.9990	0.9988	0.7966	

Table 1: Comparison of computed energies, their root mean square relative errors, and predicted wave function fidelities across 10 trials for each of the first 10 energy states of a quantum harmonic oscillator with $\omega = 1$, using different boundary constraint enforcement methods. The slight exceedance of fidelity above unity observed for $n = 0$ under HBC₂ is due to imperfect normalization.

Figure 3: Energy eigenvalues of a quantum harmonic oscillator with $\omega = 1$ predicted by the model during training epochs (left). Although shown for a single training run, similar convergence behavior was observed across multiple runs. Values of α learned by the model under HBC₂ for each wave function across training runs (right). The dashed horizontal line indicates the value of α in the closed form of the wave functions.

levels, spending fewer epochs trapped near the energy of the previous state and gradually approaching the correct eigenvalue. In contrast, with HBC₂ and HBC₃, the model tends to remain longer near the energy of the previously

Figure 4: Differential equation residual (top) and corresponding orthogonality loss (bottom) as functions of training epochs for the fourth and fifth excited states of the harmonic oscillator.

learned state, followed by abrupt shifts to the next level, except in the case of ground state. This exception is tied to the fact that the constraint function f used in HBC₃ is the ground state wave function itself, and in this case, the network \mathbf{u}_Θ only needs to converge to the appropriate normalization constant. The initial previously-learned energy persistence for a given state is due to a

delay in minimization of the orthogonality loss \mathcal{L}_O . This is corroborated by the observation that energy transition begins only when \mathcal{L}_O starts to decrease as seen in Fig. 4 (bottom).

The average predicted energies, along with the corresponding RMSRE reported in the first and second columns of Table 1, show that the model produces energy eigenvalues consistent with the exact values given by Eq. (30), with relative errors on the order of 10^{-5} across most states, except for the last two under HBC₂ and HBC₃ implementations, which show relatively higher RMSRE. We observe a correlation between high RMSRE and low fidelity. This is to be expected, since the energies are calculated directly from the predicted wave functions.

The rise in RMSRE and drop in fidelity for the last two states using HBC₂ can be attributed to two factors. First, the convergence criteria: false convergence may occur when the model remains trapped near the energy of a previously learned state. We can prevent this by deactivating the convergence criteria until \mathcal{L}_O starts decreasing. Second, the choice of the hard constraint function f : even with substantially extended training, \mathcal{L}_O may not diminish. We ascribe the latter issue to the choice of f , as the same behavior is observed for the fifth excited state under HBC₃, in fact occurring more frequently than under HBC₂, but not under SBC and HBC₁. Even when the model identifies the correct energy for the fourth excited state with HBC₃, the precision is poor due to inadequately optimized residuals \mathcal{L}_D and \mathcal{L}_O . This too can be verified from the loss histories presented in Fig. 4. It can also be observed that the differential equation residual shows pronounced fluctuations for SBC and HBC₁, while HBC₂ and HBC₃ demonstrate relatively steady loss history.

The number of epochs required for convergence is compared in Fig. 5. SBC and HBC₁ show comparable average epochs for convergence across all states. For states up to the third excited state, HBC₂ and HBC₃ demonstrate the fastest convergence, with average training epochs under 2×10^3 and minimal variation. HBC₂ displays a steady increase in both average epochs and variability as we progress to successive excited states. A similar trend is observed for HBC₃ until the third excited state; however, for the fourth excited state, the training epoch range increases markedly, with an average of about 1.3×10^5 . HBC₁ exhibits the most rapid convergence at the upper end of the chosen energy spectrum.

We make an interesting observation regarding the convergence behavior of the neural network. At first glance, one might expect the learned wave function component \mathbf{u}_Θ to approach the form of the Hermite polynomial with

Figure 5: Comparison of model efficiency for harmonic oscillator wave functions using different boundary condition enforcement methods. Error bars indicate the minimum (left end), maximum (right end), and average (circle) training epochs.

appropriate normalization factor, and the parameter α to converge to 0.5 for all energy states (see Eq. 31). However, as shown in Fig. 3 (right), this expectation does not hold in practice. In fact, when it is fixed at 0.5, as in the case of HBC₃, the model falls short of converging to higher energy states. This indicates that allowing α to vary can play a critical role in facilitating convergence for excited states.

3.2. Hydrogen

The reduced radial wave functions obtained for the hydrogen problem are presented in Fig. 6. Unlike the harmonic oscillator results (see Fig. 2), performance here depends on the boundary constraint enforcement technique. As evident from the average fidelities listed in Table 2, the soft-constrained model and the hard-constrained model under HBC₄ achieve similar performance for $l = 0$, though performance degrades with increasing n . The decline is especially pronounced under HBC₁, with a substantial drop in fidelity observed for $n = 4$. For $l > 0$, SBC struggles to yield satisfactory results, while both HBC₁ and HBC₄ maintain reasonable performance for $l = 1$ and select

Figure 6: Reduced radial wave functions of a spinless electron in the hydrogen atom produced by the model using soft boundary constraints and various hard-constraint ansätze. SBC results are shown for $l = 0$, and only the improved HBC_4 result is shown for $n = 4$, $l = 1$.

l	n	$\bar{E} (E_h)$			RMSRE			\bar{F}			Avg. Epochs		
		SBC	HBC_1	HBC_4	SBC	HBC_1	HBC_4	SBC	HBC_1	HBC_4	SBC	HBC_1	HBC_4
0	1	-0.4864	-0.5000	-0.5000	2.7×10^{-2}	2.2×10^{-5}	2.0×10^{-4}	0.9994	1.0193	1.0001	52,003	28,733	16,763
2	2	-0.1232	-0.1249	-0.1249	1.4×10^{-2}	1.5×10^{-3}	6.0×10^{-4}	0.9990	1.0108	1.0017	45,110	151,790	39,740
3	3	-0.0545	-0.0552	-0.0553	2.0×10^{-2}	8.3×10^{-3}	6.4×10^{-3}	0.9932	0.9780	0.9973	101,210	200,000	62,010
4	4	-0.0272	-0.0229	-0.0310	3.2×10^{-1}	2.8×10^{-1}	1.2×10^{-2}	0.9515	0.6817	0.9846	162,760	59,160	137,240
1	2		-0.1250	-0.1247		2.0×10^{-4}	2.7×10^{-3}		0.9995	0.9990		165,962	73,463
	3		-0.0552	-0.0539		8.1×10^{-3}	3.1×10^{-2}		0.9927	0.9755		200,000	73,730
2	3		-0.0554	-0.0505		3.6×10^{-3}	9.3×10^{-2}		0.9946	0.9180		200,001	208,513

Table 2: Comparison of computed energies, their root mean square relative errors, predicted wave function fidelities, and training epochs for the hydrogen atom over 10 trials for select values of l and n using different boundary constraints enforcement techniques.

states with $l = 2$. However, HBC_1 ceases to produce accurate wave functions beyond $l = 2$, $n = 3$. A similar trend is observed in the predicted energy

eigenvalues.

Furthermore, the average training epochs for the hydrogen problem is apparently higher than that for the harmonic oscillator, with a considerable surge for all excited states relative to the ground state.

The performance of HBC₄ is significantly enhanced when utilizing the adaptive learning rate schedule and training the model until the differential equation residual falls below a certain threshold. The results of this training procedure are summarized in Table 3. This improvement in efficiency is partly due to sampling collocation points from an interval dependent on n (smaller interval for lower n) as opposed to a constant boundary interval for all the states. For this and the subsequent case, we used the default initialization instead of starting from previously learned states for excited states.

l	n	$E(E_h)$	RE	F	\mathcal{L}_D	Epochs	α
0	1	-0.5000	1.2×10^{-7}	1.0002	5.0×10^{-8}	19,097	0.340902
	2	-0.1250	7.8×10^{-7}	1.0000	5.0×10^{-8}	84,964	0.334687
	3	-0.0556	5.4×10^{-5}	1.0000	5.0×10^{-8}	54,930	0.239097
	4	-0.0312	9.0×10^{-4}	0.9993	1.4×10^{-7}	800,000	0.150291
1	2	-0.1250	6.6×10^{-6}	1.0000	5.0×10^{-8}	55,399	0.320152
	3	-0.0556	8.5×10^{-5}	1.0000	5.0×10^{-8}	21,945	0.313017
	4	-0.0312	4.3×10^{-4}	0.9998	7.17×10^{-8}	800,000	0.224424
2	3	-0.0556	8.8×10^{-5}	1.0000	5.8×10^{-8}	800,000	0.352132

Table 3: Results for the hydrogen problem HBC₄ obtained with adaptive learning rate based on current differential equation residual and variable collocation boundaries dependent on principal quantum number n . The lower bound for Ξ_c is set to 0.01, and the upper bound is chosen as 20, 30, 50, and 65 for $n = 1, 2, 3,$ and 4 , respectively. \mathcal{L}_D indicates the final differential equation residual. The final learnable parameters α are different from $\frac{1}{n}$ (see Eq. (37)). For the model used, $N_h = 50$.

3.3. Yukawa Potential

Since using adaptive learning rate improved the results for the Coulomb potential, we apply the same strategy to the Yukawa potential. The reduced radial wave functions obtained from our experiments are shown in Fig. 7. For comparison, wave functions calculated by numerically solving Eq. (A.3) are also shown in the figure. We see that for states with zero azimuthal quantum number ($l = 0$), model predictions and numerical wave functions agree well with each other with the fidelity between these two wave functions

Figure 7: Reduced radial wave functions for the Yukawa potential with $g = 0.025$ and $V_0 = \sqrt{2}$ predicted by the hard-constrained PINN under HBC_4 compared with those calculated from numerical method. For higher states, slight discrepancies are seen as r increases.

Figure 8: Differential equation residual (top) and corresponding orthogonality loss (bottom) as functions of training epochs for various wave functions of the Yukawa potential, obtained using the hard-constrained model with HBC_4 .

l	n	$\bar{E} (E_h)$	RMSRE		\bar{F}	\mathcal{L}_D	Avg. Epochs
			Numerical	SUSY			
0	1	-0.95092	5.5×10^{-5}	3.3×10^{-6}	0.9999	9.9×10^{-8}	10,590
	2	-0.20354	9.5×10^{-6}	9.5×10^{-6}	0.9999	9.9×10^{-8}	38,000
	3	-0.06865	1.2×10^{-5}	*	0.9999	9.9×10^{-8}	135,750
1	2	-0.20298	5.8×10^{-5}	5.8×10^{-5}	0.9998	9.9×10^{-8}	85,820
	3	-0.06814	2.9×10^{-4}	7.7×10^{-5}	0.9997	9.9×10^{-8}	194,370
2	3	-0.06711	4.4×10^{-4}	3.0×10^{-4}	0.9997	1.1×10^{-7}	599,990

Table 4: Results for the Yukawa potential with $g = 0.025$ and $V_0 = \sqrt{2}$, obtained using HBC₄ with an adaptive learning rate. The figures represent averages over 10 trials. Reported epochs indicate the average number of training iterations required for the differential equation residual to reach the values shown under \mathcal{L}_D . * indicates that the required value is not reported in the reference. For the model used, $N_h = 50$.

close to 1 as reported in Table 4, whereas the fidelity drops slightly for states with higher azimuthal quantum number. The evolution of two losses: differential equation residual \mathcal{L}_D and orthogonality residual \mathcal{L}_O is presented in Fig. 8. We find that as the principal quantum number n increases, \mathcal{L}_D of the higher states are slow to diminish, taking up to 6×10^6 epochs to reach a satisfactorily low value of 1.1×10^{-7} , while \mathcal{L}_O typically lowers below 1×10^{-7} after around 10^4 epochs for all states.

The energy eigenvalues are presented in Table 4. Comparing the energy obtained from the network prediction with the numerical result, we see there is good agreement between these two methods with highest RMSRE for $n = 3$, $l = 2$ state, in the order of 10^{-4} .

Energy eigenvalues of Eq. (6) for Yukawa potential show dependence on l even for the same n , which is different than what is observed for the Coulomb potential. Apart from the rotational invariance, the Coulomb potential possesses an additional hidden symmetry related to the Runge–Lenz vector, resulting in energy eigenvalues that are independent of l [43]. This symmetry is formally recognized as the $SO(4)$ symmetry group. The Yukawa potential lacks this hidden symmetry due to the exponential screening factor which leads to energy levels that depend on both n and l .

In Table 4, we have also provided RMSRE between our model predictions with the energy values reported in [44] approximated by theoretical investigation using a supersymmetry (SUSY) framework. Energies calculated from our model predictions are in excellent agreement with these energy values as well, up to an order of 10^{-4} for all the states.

4. Conclusions

In this study, we show that the method of enforcing boundary constraints in PINNs strongly affects both the accuracy of the solutions and the convergence behavior. The differential equation residual shows high fluctuations for soft-constrained models during training, whereas for hard-constrained models that mimic the required asymptotic behavior, it decreases steadily. For the harmonic oscillator, the soft-constrained model provides accurate solutions for ground and excited states but takes high number of epochs to train. The hard-constrained model can be more efficient for lower-energy states. However, its performance depends heavily on the chosen ansatz as certain functions lead to accurate and fast convergence, whereas others fail to converge to correct higher excited states and can even be less efficient than the soft-constrained model. Hard constraints that reflect the asymptotic behavior of the solutions works best for the central potentials.

Introducing a learnable parameter in the hard constraint ansatz proves advantageous over hard-coding it, as the network often discovers an optimal value different from the one expected from the analytical solution or the asymptotic behavior. For excited states, we recommend experimenting with both training from scratch and initializing the network with parameters from previously learned states.

We find that the tanh activation outperforms the sinusoidal activation, particularly for the central potentials, despite the latter being more commonly used in the PINN literature. The choice of loss weights (λ parameters) is also critical for proper optimization. Solution accuracy is greatly enhanced by adopting adaptive learning rate scheduling based on the current differential equation residual and greater efficiency in terms of training epochs can be achieved by using smaller collocation set bounds for lower states.

Our experiments reveal that relatively small models (e.g., with only 20 hidden neurons) train faster on CPUs than on GPUs, likely due to CPU–GPU communication overhead. Conversely, for larger models, GPUs remain the preferable.

5. Limitations

The results reported in this study are obtained using a single-hidden-layer neural network with a fixed number of neurons. We do not explore other network architectures and depths. Although the default PyTorch weight

initialization (Kaiming/He initialization) is used, it is designed for ReLU activations. Alternative initializations, such as Xavier initialization, may produce improved results.

PINNs are an interesting approach for solving differential equations. However, their sensitivity to hyperparameters and the high training time required on standard hardware, such as personal computers, make conventional numerical methods a more practical choice for the types of problems considered in this work.

6. Code Availability

Sample codes are available at our [GitHub repo](#).

Appendix A. Finite Difference Method

First, we define a discretized domain of 5×10^3 points in $[0.01, 50]$ as $\mathbf{r}_d = [r_0, r_1, \dots, r_n, r_{n+1}]$, with $\Delta r = r_1 - r_0$. In this discretized setting, we have

$$\left. \frac{d^2 \zeta(r)}{dr^2} \right|_{r=r_j} = \frac{\zeta_{j-1} - 2\zeta_j + \zeta_{j+1}}{\Delta r^2}; \quad r_j \in \mathbf{r}_d. \quad (\text{A.1})$$

This leads to a discretized form of Eq. (6):

$$-\frac{\hbar^2}{2m} \frac{\zeta_{j-1} - 2\zeta_j + \zeta_{j+1}}{\Delta r^2} + \left[-V_0 \frac{e^{-\beta r_j}}{r_j} + \frac{l(l+1)}{2r_j^2} \right] \zeta_j = E \zeta_j, \quad (\text{A.2})$$

where $\zeta_j = \zeta(r_j)$ are the elements of the eigenvector $\boldsymbol{\zeta}$.

Using the fact that the radial wave functions must satisfy the boundary conditions (7), $\zeta(r_0) = \zeta(r_{n+1}) = 0$, we can define the following matrices:

$$H_{n \times n} = \begin{bmatrix} -2 & 1 & 0 & 0 & \dots & 0 \\ 1 & -2 & 1 & 0 & \dots & 0 \\ 0 & 1 & -2 & 1 & \dots & 0 \\ 0 & 0 & 1 & \ddots & \ddots & \vdots \\ \vdots & \vdots & \vdots & \ddots & -2 & 1 \\ 0 & 0 & 0 & \dots & 1 & -2 \end{bmatrix},$$

$$\mathcal{V}_{n \times n} = \begin{bmatrix} \frac{e^{-\beta r_1}}{r_1} & 0 & \cdots & 0 \\ 0 & \frac{e^{-\beta r_2}}{r_2} & \cdots & 0 \\ \vdots & \vdots & \ddots & \vdots \\ 0 & 0 & \cdots & \frac{e^{-\beta r_n}}{r_n} \end{bmatrix},$$

and

$$\mathcal{M}_{n \times n} = \begin{bmatrix} \frac{1}{r_1^2} & 0 & \cdots & 0 \\ 0 & \frac{1}{r_2^2} & \cdots & 0 \\ \vdots & \vdots & \ddots & \vdots \\ 0 & 0 & \cdots & \frac{1}{r_n^2} \end{bmatrix},$$

which convert Eq. (A.2) into the following matrix eigenvalue problem:

$$\left[\frac{\hbar^2}{2m \Delta r^2} H - V_0 \mathcal{V} + \frac{l(l+1)}{2} \mathcal{M} \right] \zeta = E \zeta. \quad (\text{A.3})$$

We solve this using scipy package in Python [42] for E and ζ .

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